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DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES OF STUDENTS IN COMPOSITION CLASSES IN PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Annotation. *The article is devoted to one of the most urgent problems of the visual arts, teaching the subject of composition in higher educational institutions, it reveals the general didactic principles of the formation of compositional abilities of students and different approaches to its determination in the writings of foreign and local researchers.*

Key words: *artist-teacher, visual arts, painting, composition, methodology, abilities, artistic image, creativity, perception.*

In order to determine the priority areas for the systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising to a qualitatively new level the process of training independently thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities, modernizing higher education, developing the social sphere and sectors of the economy based on advanced educational technologies, a Decree by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and adopted the "Concept for the development of the system of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". It refers to the introduction of advanced standards of higher education, in particular, a phased transition from education, curricula, which are aimed at obtaining theoretical knowledge, to an education system aimed at developing practical skills based on international experience. Raising the content of higher education to a qualitatively new level, establishing a system for training highly qualified personnel who are able to find their place in the labor market, make a worthy contribution to the stable development of the social sphere and economic sectors.[1]

Teaching the subject of composition in the visual arts is one of the main subjects in the preparation of a future teacher-artist in a secondary school. The issues of methodological support of the process of teaching students the methods and techniques of images in the composition are partially considered in the studies of local and foreign artists-teachers. The theme of personality, its self-realization has been raised in the history of philosophical thought from the times of Antiquity and the Renaissance to modern times.

The development of compositional abilities can be attributed to special abilities. The formation of compositional abilities is due to the specifics of pictorial activity. The specificity of pictorial activity is determined by the quality and set of artistic material, pictorial means used to create an image. Painting requires a special vision of the forms of drawing a composition.

Teaching the subject of composition, carried out in a pedagogical university, is based on the principles of general didactics and takes into account the specifics of the subject "Composition", which is characterized by techniques and techniques for depicting painting. The theoretical study of the problem of artistic abilities of future teachers has been widely developed in the works of domestic teachers and psychologists of Uzbekistan such as B.B. Baimetova, M.G. Davletshin, G.Sh. Ananyeva, E.S. Gromova, V.I. Kirienko, B.C. Kuzina, S.P. Lomova, H.H. Rostovtsev, C.JI. Rubinstein, V.N. Teplova, A.E. Terentyeva, P.P. Chistyakova, V.A. Favorsky, E.V. Shorokhov and many others, in which the formation of abilities is considered as part of the study of the process of personality formation. According to S.L. Rubinshtein, personality structure is characterized by such indicators as orientation, attitudes, interests, needs, abilities, temperament and character.

Developing the ideas of S.L. Rubinstein, K.K. Platonov, in the concept of the personality-active approach, considers personality as a psychological structure consisting of four hierarchically arranged substructures:

- lower substructure - biologically conditioned, including the properties of temperament, age and gender characteristics of the personality;
- socially formed substructure that reflects the individual characteristics of mental processes: sensations, emotions, feelings, perception, thinking, etc.;
- substructure of experience, including knowledge, skills, abilities, habits;
- the highest, socially conditioned substructure that reflects the moral qualities, interests, inclinations, ideals, worldview, beliefs of the individual, the relationship of the individual in the team.

The content of the psychological structure of the personality mediates the formation of its abilities, including the ability to visual activity. Personal characteristics determine the forms and methods of development of artistic abilities. Considering abilities as a set of personality traits that ensure successful activity, V.M. Teplov notes that they are not some kind of invariable property of a person, abilities cannot arise outside the corresponding professional activity. In the scientific literature, general and special abilities of the individual are distinguished. General abilities are such ways of interaction of the subject with the environment that are necessary for him for physical and social adaptation.

The nature of the activity determines the development of a skill that ensures the effectiveness of professional action. To determine the value of compositional abilities, it is necessary to determine their relationship with artistic abilities, since the latter indicate the direction of professional activity. In our case, the subject of activity is a composition, the construction of which presupposes the presence of artistic and creative abilities of the subject of activity.

In turn, creative abilities refer to general abilities that testify to the level of knowledge and skill of the individual: "a person creates art in art," notes L.B. Ermolaev-

Tomin. [3. S.265.]. Consider the general didactic principles described in the work of B.A. Golub [4. P.96.], regarding the process of formation of compositional abilities. The author identifies the following didactic principles: "visibility", "consciousness and activity", "accessibility", "scientific", "individual approach", "systematicity and consistency", "strength in mastering knowledge, skills and abilities", "principle of connection of theory with practice." The principle of visibility is the basic principle of the process of teaching the subject "Composition". According to K.D. Ushinsky [5. P.30.], the learning process is based on the use of both visual and auditory channels of information.

The mutual influence of two types of information on perception enhances the power of influence of each of them. This amplifying effect is called synesthesia. In other words, when the object of the image is perceived with the help of vision, supported by the auditory sense, the image becomes more vivid than when the object is perceived through one sense organ. The principle of consciousness and activity. Exploring the development of personality, K.D. Ushinsky emphasized that in education it is necessary to form an attitude to reality. A conscious attitude to the perception of image objects determines the possibility of a holistic composition. Understanding the pictorial values of the typological characteristics of the objects of perception determines the formation of the structure of the composition. At the same time, a conscious approach to working with composition is more successful with the development of the ability to analyze ideas about the process of creating and the structure of the composition and the ability to systematically organize the process of studying the pictorial image.

The principle of accessibility involves taking into account the correspondence in the learning process of the content and volume of the subject of education with the age characteristics of students, their level of intellectual and personal development. The availability of education means the possibility of consistent mastering of the theory and practice of the subject of study by students. The lack of understanding among students of the need for a phased, logically structured training in painting activities can lead to non-systematic study of educational material. At the same time, the systematic development of the ability to perceive, imagine, represent and analyze activities ensures the consistency of work with the composition. The principle of scientific character serves as the basis for the formation of the student's worldview. Appeal to scientific knowledge is a condition for the development of students' artistic abilities, based on which they can explore the principles of building a composition.

The construction of the composition can be carried out by analyzing the structure of graphic activity, including determining the attitude of students to perceived and depicted objects. In this sense, the workshop has the means to systematically explore the process of composition formation.

Any creative act is an event associated with a specific person. To create means to express your individuality. With the existence of didactic approaches in teaching

composition to students, an individual psychological and pedagogical approach to each person is necessary so that she can show her compositional abilities. An analysis of the compositional works of a group of students conducted at the Chirchik Pedagogical Institute of the Tashkent region gives grounds that the training of visual activity is more successful in creative interaction with individual work. Individual work with students in a group allows the teacher to compare creative works and show each student a possible range of compositional solutions, analyze typical mistakes in composition.

For the development of compositional abilities, the teacher must build the learning process in such a way that interdisciplinary communication is manifested in the work for the consistent formation of compositional abilities in the field of theory and practice of drawing, painting, fine art technology, psychology of creativity and perception, and pedagogy. The principle of strength in mastering knowledge, skills and abilities means the ability to apply the studied theoretical material in future pedagogical activity.

The principle of connection between theory and practice reveals the need for students to master theoretical knowledge, which could be available for use in artistic activity. This principle is the basis of the subject "Composition"; for example, knowledge of the psychological foundations of the theory of perception and imagination allows students to determine the strategy for creating an artistic image, writing an expressive composition. The principle of regularity in learning is manifested in the timely and consistent study of educational artistic material, which ensures the systematic formation of the ability to depict a composition. The principle of variability is used when creating such learning models that allow you to combine methods, forms, means and pedagogical techniques corresponding to them for the purposes of teaching composition.

The formation of compositional abilities is built on an integration basis, mediated by interdisciplinary connections. The concept of "integration" means the restoration of integrity. In the process of integrating knowledge from various fields of science and art, a holistic knowledge about the subject of study of a qualitatively different content is formed. In our case, the formation of compositional abilities in painting can be considered as a process of integrating artistic and analytical abilities aimed at studying the process of depicting an artistic composition. So, P.P. Chistyakov, in his studies of the artistic image, paid special attention to the principles of composition formation, which he called "composition". Analyzing the ideas of the Italian Renaissance architect L.B. Alberti, set out in the treatise "Ten Books on Creativity", P.P. Chistyakov defined composition as "composing, inventing, invention as an act of free creative will."

In the studies of E.G. Rechitskaya and E.A. Soshina, devoted to the development of creative action, notes the role of developmental education for the formation of special abilities. In particular, the authors refer to L.S. Vygotsky: "... Training should lead to development, focusing on the components of abilities that have not yet been fully formed in the course of such training [6. P.46.]. Based on P. Galperin's provisions on the phased formation of mental actions, at the initial stages of training it is advisable to

offer tasks aimed at studying the "external plan" (for example, manipulating surrounding objects); then tasks solved in the space of "external speech" using "visual supports" (analysis of the properties of objects); further tasks for the "internal plan" (work with images).

The formation of the components of compositional abilities is built both on the basis of experiencing the emotional and sensory experience of perception, and on the basis of an analytical study of an imaginary and represented object. The basis for the formation of compositional abilities in students of pedagogical universities should be the perception of objects of reality, the study of their perceived and imaginary meanings. The formation of compositional abilities is mediated by the development of "operational components of the imagination." Under the "operational components of the imagination" we mean images, symbols, meanings, elements of composition, the study of which determines the expressiveness of the composition. Imagination, as a cognitive process, combines the emotional and rational principles, provides the process of transformation of the artistic image.

According to S.P. Lomov, "the main lever of creativity, in addition to mastering the experience of predecessors, is the developed "imagination" - the highest form of figurative thinking. The power of imagination gives a person the ability to foresee, i.e. to feel, to see the potential for the development of a phenomenon or the possibilities contained in the material, in the structure.... [7.C. 67.]. The picturesque image is carried out thanks to the ability to imagine, transform and stylize the artistic image. Two ways of developing the imagination can be distinguished: 1. Reproductive, in which the artistic transfer of the perceptual image is carried out; 2. Transformative, when there is a free transformation of the image.

In the Surikov school of drawing (V.A. Favorsky, N.N. Volkov, E.A. Kibrik, etc.), close attention is paid to the aesthetic problems of composition. The subject of study are such laws and principles of composition as integrity, conventionality, comparison, symbolism, as well as the objective characteristics of the composition: weight, direction, balance, tension, rhythm, and others.

Analysis of the structure of the compositional image of an artistic image is a cognitive process aimed at studying its qualitative characteristics. According to B.C. Kuzin: "the ability to see and express this wholeness in a work is one of the main and ultimate goals of visual activity" [8. C.154]. For the development of compositional abilities in future teachers-artists, it is important to form their need for self-expression in painting. Stimulating the need for self-expression, the teacher develops the student's emotional and volitional qualities. The meaning of motivation lies in the search and finding of an action that corresponds to the main, fixed in life setting of the individual. This setting, as we believe, can be a setting for studying the laws of fine art, for creative self-expression, in the search for new compositional paintings in painting.

So, we can conclude that among the countless variety of forms in nature that the future artist-teacher encounters, regularity and consistency reign, the connecting thread of which is the composition. Above, we tried to correct this issue and introduce some new previously uncovered issues in the composition. Therefore, the study of the problem of teaching composition in a pedagogical university is relevant both in theoretical and practical terms. Studying and summarizing the long-term experience of scientists and painters, it is necessary to clarify a number of the most important problems associated with highlighting the features of composition and painting, issues of artistic skill, and diversity.

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